

The Fabrication of Polylactic acid (PLA) / Cellulose nanofiber (CNF) Nanocomposites with Plasticizer as Dispersing Agent

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Introduction

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) has been in the spotlight for decades as a bio-source polymer to replace petroleum-based plastics due to depletion of petroleum resources. It also has the advantage of being a biodegradable material and does not seriously affect environmental impact. PLA is used in various fields because it has good rigidity, and it is widely used in packaging and automobile fields. However, it still has low ductility and is easily broken, making it difficult to apply to soft packaging. Cellulose is the most abundant biomaterial present and is extracted from readily available biomass.¹ Recently, biodegradable composites of PLA having microcrystalline cellulose, wood fibers, wood powder, cellulose fibers, and cellulose nanowhiskers have been produced and studied.²⁻⁴ Cellulose nanofibers (CNF) have great potential for polymer matrix enhancement due to their low weight and morphological properties such as large specific surface area and high aspect ratio.⁵ Moreover, CNFs are easily agglomerated with each other because they contain a group of cellulose chains joined together by hydrogen bonding. Many researches have been carried out on the production of composite materials by adding natural-based fillers to biodegradable plastics, which are called green composites.⁶⁻¹¹ Dispersion of CNF in the PLA matrix generally improved the modulus of the composite, but the elongation at break was reduced compared to the neat PLA.¹² One difficulty with using nanocelluloses is that it is difficult to uniformly disperse them in a nonpolar polymer because of the polar surface.¹³ So it was initially limited to the solvent casting method when manufacturing cellulose nanofiber composites.¹⁴⁻²⁰ In recent years, however, PLA / CNF composite materials have been studied using a melt mixing method.^{13,21-24} The main difficulty is to supply the cellulose nanofiber to the extruder and achieve a uniform dispersion in the polymer matrix.¹⁵ This can be resolved in a number of studies by mixing cellulose nanofibers in an extruder into one of the liquids as they are fed into the extruder.²⁵⁻²⁷ In this study, PLA / CNF nanocomposites were prepared by melt mixing method with triethyl citrate (TEC) as plasticizer. And TEC has been used as a plasticizer and processing aid to facilitate CNF dispersion. The optimum plasticizer content was selected through previous studies, and cellulose nanofibers were homogenized in TEC solvent and then melt mixed with PLA. The reinforced nanocomposites were prepared with CNF contents of 0.25, 0.5, and 1 wt%. The mechanical and rheological properties of nanocomposites has been characterized. Due to the effect of the plasticization, the increase of elongation at break was confirmed. In the morphology analysis using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and 3D laser scanning microscopy, we confirmed that CNF is well dispersed in the PLA matrix. Oxygen and water vapor barrier properties of the nanocomposites were evaluated by various analytical instruments to achieve optimized property and performance.

Table 1. List of analysis equipment

Analysis equipment	Product Model
Universal Test Machine	Instron model 3367
Rheometer-rotational	Anton paar GmbH Physica MCR 302
Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy	PerkinElmer Frontier
Scanning Electron Microscope	HITACHI SU8020
3D Laser Scanning Microscope	Keyence VK-X200K
Thermal Gravimetric Analysis	TA instrument Q500
Oxygen permeability measurement	Mocon OX-TRAN 702
Dynamic mechanical analyzer	TA instrument RSA-G2

Interaction between TEC and CNF

Table 2. Interfacial Tension of the Between Solvent/Polymer and CNF, Solvent/Polymer and Solvent.

Solution Processing		Melt Processing	
Material pair	Interfacial tension γ (mN/m)	Material pair	Interfacial tension γ (mN/m)
TEC-CNF	59.33	PLA-CNF	60.18
Ethanol-CNF	50.8	TEC-CNF	59.33
TEC-Ethanol	43.1	PLA-TEC	53.17

Figure 1. Zeta potentials of TEC-CNF and ethanol-CNF solutions

Figure 2. The chemical characterization of TEC-CNF solution; (a) FTIR spectra, (b) schematic representation of CNF and TEC interaction, (c) SEM image of TEC-CNF solution with ethanol evaporated at 180 °C.

Rheological and Mechanical Properties

Figure 5. Experimentally measured tensile modulus for CNF/PLA nanocomposites compared to theoretical estimation by Cox-Krenschel; (a) f-CNF/PLA and (b) e-CNF/PLA nanocomposites.

Table 3. Mechanical Properties of the Neat PLA, f-CNF/PLA and e-CNF/PLA Nanocomposites.

Sample Code	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
Neat PLA	71.82 ± 0.96	9.50 ± 0.90	1.09 ± 0.11
f-CNF/PLA 0.25	74.66 ± 1.28	7.63 ± 0.79	1.29 ± 0.08
e-CNF/PLA 0.25	77.65 ± 0.49	7.95 ± 0.44	1.23 ± 0.05
f-CNF/PLA 0.5	73.31 ± 1.01	7.66 ± 0.81	1.29 ± 0.05
e-CNF/PLA 0.5	78.65 ± 0.81	8.19 ± 0.44	1.27 ± 0.06
f-CNF/PLA 1	71.44 ± 0.54	8.62 ± 1.14	1.05 ± 0.15

Table 4. Mechanical Properties of the t-PLA and f-CNF/t-PLA Nanocomposites.

Sample Code	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
t-PLA	35.75 ± 0.75	323.62 ± 37.87	0.63 ± 0.03
f-CNF/t-PLA 0.25	39.74 ± 0.12	339.26 ± 39.05	0.71 ± 0.04
f-CNF/t-PLA 0.5	42.15 ± 1.21	325.71 ± 41.07	0.89 ± 0.07
f-CNF/t-PLA 1	43.02 ± 1.49	308.24 ± 67.16	1.06 ± 0.09

Figure 4. (a) The storage modulus as a function of CNF loading for CNF/PLA nanocomposites at angular frequency of 0.1 1/s and (b) Van Gurp-Palmen plots for CNF/PLA nanocomposites.

Morphological, Oxygen barrier and Dynamic mechanical Properties

Figure 5. SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces of CNF/PLA nanocomposites:

(a) 0.25 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (b) 0.5 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (c) 1 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (d) 0.25 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (e) 0.5 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (f) 1 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (g) 0.25 wt% t-CNF/PLA, (h) 0.5 wt% t-CNF/PLA, (i) 1 wt% t-CNF/PLA.

Figure 6. CNF agglomerates size distribution and binarized microscopy image of CNF/PLA nanocomposites; (a) 0.25 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (b) 0.5 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (c) 1 wt% f-CNF/PLA, (d) 0.25 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (e) 0.5 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (f) 1 wt% e-CNF/PLA, (g) 0.25 wt% t-CNF/PLA, (h) 0.5 wt% t-CNF/PLA, (i) 1 wt% t-CNF/PLA.

Sample Code	Oxygen Permeability (cc-mm ² -day-atm)	Sample Code	Oxygen Permeability (cc-mm ² -day-atm)
Neat PLA	32.26 ± 1.24	t-PLA	34.54 ± 2.17
f-CNF/PLA 0.25	31.55 ± 0.08	t-CNF/PLA 0.25	21.23 ± 0.40
e-CNF/PLA 0.25	32.87 ± 0.55	t-CNF/PLA 0.5	18.41 ± 0.07
f-CNF/PLA 0.5	22.52 ± 0.07	t-CNF/PLA 1	16.99 ± 0.85
e-CNF/PLA 0.5	26.43 ± 0.24		
f-CNF/PLA 1	29.86 ± 0.12		
e-CNF/PLA 1	15.88 ± 1.36		

Table 5. Oxygen Permeability Properties of the Neat PLA, f-CNF/PLA, e-CNF/PLA and t-CNF/PLA Nanocomposites.

Figure 7. Storage modulus, E' of (a) f-CNF/PLA, (b) e-CNF/PLA, and (c) t-CNF/PLA nanocomposites, and tan delta of (d) f-CNF/PLA, (e) e-CNF/PLA, and (f) t-CNF/PLA nanocomposites.